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Anastasiia Balan, Oksana Krupa

Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts, Kyiv, Ukraine

Analysis of Modern PR Strategies in the Show Business Industry

Abstract: *Introduction.* In the modern world, the show business industry is central to the cultural and entertainment life of society. Show business is an important mechanism for shaping social stereotypes, influencing mass consciousness, creating trends and defining cultural values. Professional PR has become an integral part of successful activities in the show business industry. It plays a key role in building a positive image of artists, production companies, film companies, music bands and other market participants. *Purpose and methods.* The purpose of the study is to theoretically analyze modern PR strategies in the show business industry, to study and understand modern approaches to PR communications in this area, taking into account technological, social and economic trends. The methodological basis is the systemic and interdisciplinary approaches, as well as methods of general scientific, terminological, expert, observation and comparison, critical analysis, abstract and logical modeling. *Results.* The types of PR, the essence and the role of PR strategies in the show business industry are defined. The essence of using social media as a PR tool is revealed. Modern PR strategies in the show business industry are substantiated. *Conclusions.* The study indicates that factors such as authenticity, consistency and cooperation with influential personalities are of great importance in modern PR strategies. In addition, the effectiveness of PR strategies is also determined by the ability to adapt to changes in society, responding to challenges and trends. There is a need to integrate PR strategies into the overall marketing strategy of companies and artists, which will ensure their consistency and interaction with other types of marketing.

Keywords: PR strategy, show business industry, social media, public relations.

* Research Supervisor – Professor Olena Khlystun

1. Introduction

The problem formulation. The relevance of the study lies in the need to understand the effectiveness and adaptability of communication strategies used by the show business industry in the modern digital environment. The importance of the topic is also due to profound transformations in the socio-cultural space and media landscape. In today's world, the show business industry is not just an entertainment platform, it is a complex system where not only the talent of the artist but also the skill in building his or her public image is of great importance. The growing influence of social media, changing consumer habits of the audience, and the evolution of media platforms create new challenges for PR strategies in this industry. The analysis of modern PR strategies in the show business industry will take into account various aspects, including the use of social media, public relations and branding events, sponsorship programs, and crisis PR. The results of the study will help to reveal current trends in the field of PR in the show business industry and provide recommendations on how to optimize communication strategies to achieve maximum impact and success. Ukrainian show business today is undergoing significant positive changes, determined by the final separation from the Russian cultural and information space. This opens up new prospects for Ukrainian artists, emphasizing the need for effective promotion of personal brands for both performers and show business PR professionals.

State study of the problem. The conceptual foundations of socio-cultural management, which is the theoretical and methodological basis for strategic management in show business, are discussed in the works of Yaroslav Martynyshyn, Olena Khlystun, Olena Kostyuchenko, and Yelena Kovalenko (Martynyshyn et al., 2020, 2022, 2023; Martynyshyn & Khlystun, 2018; Martynyshyn & Kostyuchenko, 2018; Martynyshyn & Kovalenko, 2018; Kovalenko, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023), Mykhailo Poplavskyi (1999, 2001), Philip Kotler (Kotler et al., 2017; Kotler et al., 2022) and other scholars.

Public relations in the show business industry is a rather relevant and studied object in the foreign scientific field. Scientists such as Sam Black (1995), Rex Harlow (1976), Shel Holtz (2002), Rob Brown (2009), Kiran Shahid (2023), Al Ries and Laura Ries (2004), Alex Singleton (2014), David Scott (2020), Gini Dietrich (2014), Ronald Smith (2017) and others consider the theoretical aspects of organization, practical solutions, methods and features of PR in show business.

Ukraine also has an active academic community that studies public relations in various fields, including the show business industry. It is worth noting such scholars as Valentin Korolko and Oksana Nekrasova (2009), Oleksandr Serkov (2022), Iryna Muntian, Olena Holubonkova and Viktoriya Milcheva (2023),

Oleg Chubuk (2020), Elina Slobodianiuk (n.d.), Olena Paplinska (2021), Denys Zakharov (2017), Vira Haponenko and Volodymyr Rykhlik (2015), Oleksandr Romanovskiy, Nataliia Sereda and Yevheniia Vorobiova (2018), Olena Khlystun (2022). Domestic researchers pay attention to public relations strategies, adaptation and development of theoretical concepts and methods of PR, reputation management, crisis PR, and the use of social media in building an image.

Unresolved issues. However, many aspects and new trends in the use of PR strategies in the show business industry remain poorly understood, which is why the level of study of the problem indicates the need for a deep and comprehensive analysis. Therefore, existing works leave many questions open, which justifies the relevance of further research in this area.

In the context of analyzing modern PR strategies in the show business industry, there are a number of unresolved issues and topics that should be considered. First of all, it is the impact of digitalization on PR in the show business industry. With the development of digital media and social platforms, communication strategies have changed radically. The second issue concerns ethical aspects in show business PR. The third is interaction with the audience in the digital age. In addition, an important issue concerns the measurement of the effectiveness of PR events in the show business industry. It is also important to consider the issue of crisis management in the PR industry of show business.

2. Purpose and methods

The purpose and research tasks. The purpose of the study is to theoretically analyze modern PR strategies in the show business industry, to study and understand modern approaches to PR communications in this area, taking into account technological, social and economic trends.

Objectives of the study:

- analysis of the current state of the show business industry and its relationship with PR strategies;
- study of the main trends in the field of PR and communications in the show business industry;
- identification of key principles and methods of using PR in the show business industry;
- analysis of the effectiveness of modern PR strategies in supporting brands and projects in the show business;
- identification of promising areas of development and innovation in the field of PR in the show business industry;
- formulating recommendations for improving PR strategies in the show business industry in order to increase their effectiveness and impact.

Methodology and methods. The research methodology is based on a combination of systemic and interdisciplinary approaches: the first approach allows us to consider the PR of the show business industry as an integral system of interconnected elements and subsystems, which makes it possible to study complex PR processes, taking into account their diversity and dynamics in this area. The second, interdisciplinary approach combines knowledge and methods of various scientific disciplines to create a holistic picture of organizational PR processes, taking into account various aspects (economic, managerial, cultural, social, psychological, etc.) and allowing to consider this problem in detail from all sides.

The study used both general scientific and special methods. The terminological method was used to clarify the essence of the conceptual apparatus of the study of PR strategies in the show business industry. The method of critical analysis of scientific literature was used to systematize and summarize the main theoretical provisions of the research topic. The methods of observation and comparison, as well as analysis and synthesis were used to analyze the current state of the show business industry and its relationship with PR strategies. To identify and predict promising areas of development and innovation in the field of PR in the show business industry, the method of abstract and logical modeling was applied. The system-structural, functional and expert methods were used to develop recommendations for improving PR strategies in the show business industry in order to increase their efficiency and impact.

Information base. The research is based on the works of well-known Ukrainian and foreign scholars on the issue of socio-cultural management and strategic PR management in show business, as well as on the author's observations of a group of vertically integrated companies in this area. The study is also based on the laws of Ukraine, including the Law of Ukraine "On Media" (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 2022), the Law of Ukraine "On Advertising" (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 1996), the Law of Ukraine "On Information" (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 1992) and other regulatory documents.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Types of PR, the essence and role of PR strategies in the show business industry

In the international Webster's Dictionary (Webster, 1828), one can read the following definition: "Public relations is the science and art of establishing mutual understanding and goodwill between a person, firm or institution and the public" (p. 77).

The influence of PR methods can be not only positive but also negative, because it depends on the skills of the person who manages and owns public

relations technologies and their implementation. That is why we can often observe that the role of some PR strategies is seen as manipulating people's minds, while others are seen as educating. As the practice of mass communications shows, today, in addition to public relations based on truth, knowledge and full awareness, we are faced with the emergence of distorted forms of PR based on manipulative technologies.

Show business has always been a battleground for audience attention, fame, and success. However, along with the brilliant light of the spotlight and the red carpet, there is a dark side where the use of black PR becomes an effective tool for achieving certain goals. This is an activity that aims to destroy the positive image of an artist, organization, or company.

First and foremost, black PR is a business tool. And the fact in whose hands it ends up will determine what it will bring – good or evil. Black PR has already taken away roles from Hollywood actor Johnny Depp, tarnished the reputation of film director Harvey Weinstein, and forced Bill Clinton to resign from the presidency. But it is important to understand that black PR is not an art of doing evil, it is a methodology of how to use negative information to gain justice, decency, and an advantage in the market. At the same time, especially in show business, black PR is used with completely opposite intentions – to attract attention and increase interest in a particular product or person through pseudo-scandals, sensational confessions, and extraordinary actions. This makes it possible to get into rating programs on television, radio, and on the pages of popular publications. Interestingly, negative information is perceived by the public more readily than positive information, so black PR is one of the favorite methods of influence among those who want to gain popularity quickly.

A striking example is the conflict between Taylor Swift and Kanye West. First, the controversy arose during the 2009 MTV Video Music Awards, when Kanye West interrupted Taylor Swift's award presentation by making hateful comments. This episode led to a lot of discussion in the media and social networks. Later, controversy arose over the lyrics of Kanye West's song "Famous", where unacceptable words were directed at Swift. This confrontation can be viewed as a black PR strategy, as it aroused great public interest and increased the popularity of both artists.

Another type of PR is "yellow", which, thanks to its brightness, symbolizes shocking public relations. This is a way of communication that is focused on urgent attention. Of course, the authenticity of a fact is not taken into account in this system. The main idea is to get you to read the news, to focus on a vivid picture. This method is most often used in show business or politics. Outrage, fried facts, and scandals are what they use, almost like the tabloid press.

"Brown" PR is very similar in its content and form of information presentation to fascist propaganda – aggressive chauvinism, Nazism, the ideology

of the cult of the strong personality, the system of “targeting” and speculation – all these are signs of a communication system that relies on a specific global fact or a negative reaction, using them as a basis for promoting its own interests.

In addition to black, brown and yellow technologies PR technologies, we should also distinguish the “pink” PR. This is a set of methods for creating and using conventional legends and myths. According to *Friedrich Nietzsche* (1878), their goal is to create a “cover of illusions” that people constantly need (p. 205). The reasons are different for everyone, some due to a strong tendency to dream, others due to unfulfilled expectations or the influence of advertising messages and political propaganda. It is important to note that “pink” PR technologies are not always used for the purpose of deception. In some cases, such approaches can serve as a stimulus for social optimism by immersing people in the prospects of future well-being, which is especially useful in difficult times of mass uncertainty, despondency and social depression (*Figure 1*).

Figure 1. PR Types
Source: own development

Sam Black (1995) said: “White” PR is the art of understanding, information openness, and providing indisputable information” (p. 178). Many experts are convinced that this approach may be ineffective in Ukrainian realities, while others, on the contrary, are convinced of the opposite. In Ukraine, the expression “white” PR means honest advertising on behalf of the object itself, and is used to denote the concept opposite to “black” PR. In this variant, public opinion formation is based on openness and means that information about the PR object is presented in accordance with the truth and facts, while competitors are not mentioned or attacked. “White” PR focuses on highlighting the company's advantages.

It is also worth paying attention to such a close communication tool to PR as propaganda. There is an opinion that PR and propaganda are almost identical in their goals, as they use similar technologies to influence the mass consciousness. On the other hand, many PR professionals believe that it is wrong to compare their activities with propaganda (Romanov, 2023, pp. 24-29). A summary of the main differences between PR and propaganda is presented (*Table 1*).

Table 1. Differences between PR and propaganda

PR	Propaganda
Understanding	Beliefs
Harmony	A call to action
Constructive cooperation	Differentiation and confrontation
Providing positive information	Disinformation, slander of the enemy, lies
Sincerity and openness	Concealment, insincerity
Ethics of freedom and responsibility	Imposition of will, arbitrariness

Source: developed on the basis of Romanov (2023)

A PR strategy in the show business industry is based on a business strategy or business model and the main areas of activity. The PR strategy reveals the vectors of image, reputation and information policy. As a rule, it is developed for consistent and structured public action, positioning and communication with different groups of target audiences.

A PR strategy is an algorithm that a company should follow in its public activities to fulfill its tasks, achieve its goals or strengthen them.

Although the process of developing a PR strategy in show business falls on the shoulders of public relations and communications departments, external experts are usually involved in the creation of this product. An outsider's view of the company's structure can bring a new direction to strategic planning, which will have a positive impact on the company's image and reputation.

Since external experts usually have experience in performing similar tasks, their knowledge allows them to assess risks and focus on the really necessary tasks.

Researching market conditions, trends, and different audience segments is an integral part of a communications and PR agency's work. This allows them to provide truly relevant services. Ideas and solutions offered by external experts are in line with current trends, as well as standards and communication technologies. Research on socio-economic behavior, which reflects the internal attitude of the organization's employees to the conditions, content, and final results of activities, is more effective with the involvement of external experts to avoid distortion of facts.

Everyone involved in public relations needs a public relations strategy. Strategies are necessary to achieve the company's goals. Therefore, each step should bring the company closer to its global goals or, if the goals have already been achieved, maintain its position.

The structure of the strategy is created at will and takes into account all the peculiarities of the business and the market, but, of course, some elements are mandatory for show PR:

- 1) analysis and segmentation of the target audience;
- 2) analysis of the competitive environment and identification of key competitive advantages;
- 3) analysis of the public and information space and drawing up a media portrait;
- 4) defining the mission and vision of the organization;
- 5) positioning and development of key messages;
- 6) communication channels and tools;
- 7) identification of reputational risks;
- 8) creation of crisis management mechanisms;
- 9) identification of key speakers and their roles;
- 10) creating a media database.

3.2. Use of social media as a PR tool

In the modern world, social media plays a key role in shaping and maintaining a positive image of companies, brands, and personalities in the show business industry. Using social media as a PR tool allows you to create direct contact with the audience and interact with it in real time.

One of the key aspects of using social media in PR is the ability to create content that engages and interacts with the audience. Thanks to various platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, YouTube, PR teams can create interesting visual content, videos and texts that meet the interests and needs of their audience.

In addition, social media provides an opportunity to interact with the audience through comments, messages, and reactions. This allows you to create deeper relationships with consumers, increasing trust and influence.

Social media is a powerful tool for identifying and resolving crises. Thanks to the rapid dissemination of information, companies and individuals can quickly respond to negative situations, provide explanations and correct mistakes, which helps to maintain their reputation and the trust of the audience.

Social media is the basis of the new media space, embodied in various forms – text, visual, audio and video materials – and distributed through various forums, blogs and microblogs (Blogger, WordPress, Twitter, etc.), wiki directories (e.g. Wikipedia), social networking sites (Facebook, Friends, MySpace, LinkedIn, etc.), online games and virtual worlds (e.g., World of Warcraft, The Sims Online), video and photo sharing (e.g., YouTube, Flickr, Instagram), video conferencing, bulletin boards, video conferencing, RSS feeds, and much more. The term “social media” refers to the use of web and mobile technologies to transform communication into an interactive dialog.

Social media is a powerful tool for organizations and brands that not only provides opportunities for direct and immediate organizational communication

but also allows them to return to the ideal foundation of PR – building and maintaining relationships – and change the negative stereotypes that usually haunt the PR industry. In other words, the use of social media is an appropriate and effective tool for realizing what James Grunig and Todd Hunt (1984) call the ideal model of public relations (two-way symmetry).

Digital PR is public relations conducted electronically via the Internet. As for the use of Internet tools in PR activities, different researchers distinguish (Kotler et al., 2017):

- e-mail;
- World Wide Web (websites);
- virtual communities;
- blogs/microblogs;
- wikis;
- RSS;
- podcasts/videotapes;
- social networks;
- online PR (online media).

It is important to note that the Internet as a mass communication channel has both positive and negative aspects. On the one hand, it is the most mobile and independent source of information among the media. On the other hand, the ease of creating new information channels in the media leads to more and more of them. This can disperse the online audience. From the public relations point of view, social media is a constantly growing number of potential consumers and clients who are always in contact with each other. Many companies already include social media strategies in their PR plans. Blogs, a column on a specialized media outlet's website, reports and articles on your own website are a great way to provide information that is beneficial to the company. After all, in the event of a negative story, these materials will be a lifeline to restore a positive image.

A modern PR specialist needs to implement his or her projects in the context of social dialog. In addition, social media helps to further reveal the essence of PR – to create and tell stories, to communicate with the public and to achieve understanding. Today, it is extremely important to be part of such a dialog, otherwise, the conversation can go in a different direction that cannot be controlled, so it is imperative to be involved in it. In other words, social media cannot be managed, but it is possible to manage an organization's communications.

Today there is no single classification of social media. That is why *Oleksandr Kurban* (2013), a national expert in the field of social communications, proposes a classification system in the form of types, structural features and development technologies. The author distinguishes the following types of social networks: social contact networks (Facebook), blogs (Blog.Liga.net),

microblogs (Twitter), file-sharing sites (YouTube, Flickr), social news networks (Reddit), wiki projects (Wikipedia), bookmarking sites (Bookmarks), virtual worlds (Habbo.com), podcasts and multi-instrument media (SAY.TV).

In Ukraine, the most popular social networks are Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and YouTube. Each of them has different users depending on their income, age, occupation, and interests. The number of social media users in Ukraine is growing rapidly. The benefits of using social media include:

- the ability to easily target the target audience;
- interactivity, which allows for immediate assessment of consumer reactions;
- creative space, as there are no clear content restrictions;
- social media tends to create new opportunities to maintain consumer interest;
- promotion tools are constantly updated.

To work in social media, PR professionals must clearly understand why an organization uses social media and develop specific goals and PR strategies. To do this, they need to study the Internet space, social networks, audiences, types of communications, as well as leaders and activists of the platforms they plan to work with. It is worth noting that traditional means of public relations should not be abandoned. In order to achieve the goals and improve public relations, it is necessary to combine traditional and electronic communications in the activities of specialists.

3.3. Modern PR strategies in the show business industry

Modern PR strategies in the show business industry are used for numerous purposes and objectives, as show business, like any other industry, needs to effectively manage its own image and communicate with the audience. PR strategies help to increase the recognition of artists, movies, music and other products of the show business industry among the target audience. PR campaigns are aimed at maintaining a positive image of famous personalities, companies, films, etc., publishing positive news and stories, organizing charity events, and participating in social and cultural projects.

PR strategies are important for managing negative events and crisis situations that may arise in the show business industry. An important aspect of modern PR strategies is the development of interaction with the audience through social media, websites, blogs and other online platforms, which allows you to connect with fans, collect feedback and respond to their wishes and suggestions.

Not surprisingly, the impact of PR methods can be both positive and negative, as it depends on the skills of the person who manages and owns public relations technologies and their implementation. That is why we can often observe that the role of some PR strategies is seen as manipulating people's minds, while others are seen as educating. Effective PR strategies in the show

business industry are crucial for the stability, development and popularity of artists, producers and companies. This is justified by several key aspects. First, show business is built on images and reputation. Successful artists and companies need to manage their image, creating a positive perception among viewers and content consumers. Effective PR strategies help to maintain and develop this image, ensuring popularity and positive perception. Secondly, in the world of show business, new projects and creative ideas are constantly emerging that require effective promotion and advertising. PR specialists act as managers of this process, creating strategies to draw attention to new works, films, albums, TV shows and other projects.

The show business industry is very sensitive to crises and negative news. Effective PR strategies allow for a timely and professional response to such incidents, reducing the negative impact on the reputation of artists and companies. PR specialists create strategies to maintain communication with the audience, attract new fans, and retain the existing fan base.

Effective PR strategies in the showbiz industry perform a variety of functions, ranging from image building to crisis management, making them an integral part of success in this industry.

Analyzing the correlation between cognitive, activity and personal factors, especially soft skills that are not directly related to a specific field, it can be argued that the greatest attention should be paid to the development of personal qualities in the training of public relations specialists. The main elements of successful PR activities are: common sense, organizational skills, friendliness, objectivity, criticality, imagination and the ability to understand other people's points of view, attention to detail, and curiosity.

Interpersonal skills help you build relationships with professionals you have to communicate with in your work, such as media representatives, sponsors, agents, managers, and stylists. It is also important to be able to handle scandals and negative attacks, regardless of whether the “star” is guilty or not.

The rapid development of social media provides competitors and other stakeholders with endless opportunities to negatively highlight any situation and stir up conflict. Strategies need to be developed to respond to media inquiries, reassure the public, and resolve scandals and conflicts.

Surviving various crises can be one of the most important tasks for publicists in the entertainment industry.

The main areas of research on PR in show business are:

1) a clear definition of the goals of PR in show business. This is influenced by a specific morphological element of art, as there are differences in the goals, objectives and methods of public relations in the field of television, cinema and music performance;

2) identifying the peculiarities of public relations in different areas of art;

- 3) determining the specifics of working with artists and actors in terms of their image;
- 4) to analyze the process of public relations in show business;
- 5) to reveal the specifics of public relations in show business;
- 6) formation of various aspects of key competencies for the development of future professionals in the field of show business.

Show business professionals need to understand the historical features of show business and related creative disciplines, the role, purpose and main tasks of PR in show business, PR tools for effective influence on public consciousness, methods of formulating PR strategies and evaluating their effectiveness and potential, image techniques, branding and naming, the essence of creating a corporate identity, techniques and methods of promoting products through the media, and opportunities for effective information dissemination.

Modern professionals should also be able to write scripts and draft speeches, organize and support communication events and PR campaigns in show business, formulate information content and create PR products. Therefore, the study of various aspects of key competencies for the development of future professionals in the field of show business is one of the main tasks facing modern humanities research.

The show business industry uses a variety of PR strategies to raise awareness of artists, movies, music and other entertainment products. Modern PR strategies used in this industry:

- 1) media tour and press conferences – the strategy consists of a planned set of events aimed at attracting media attention. It may include a tour of an artist or a team to different cities to meet with journalists, TV and radio programs, as well as organizing press conferences to present new projects or announce events;
- 2) cooperation with influencers and bloggers – artists cooperate with influencers and bloggers to get a wider audience reach. It is realized in the form of joint projects, advertising, or sponsorships;
- 3) use of social media. Social media is a powerful tool for support and promotion in the show business industry. Artists are actively using platforms such as Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, and YouTube to communicate with fans, post event reports, announcements, and advertise their projects;
- 4) participation in charity events and social campaigns. Many artists use their popularity to support various charitable and social initiatives. This not only helps to increase their public profile, but also creates a positive image in the global community;
- 5) user-generated content. This strategy involves engaging fans and viewers in creating their own content related to artists or their projects. This can be in the form of contests, hashtags, or challenges that encourage users to share their impressions and creativity.

To improve PR strategies in the showbiz industry and increase their effectiveness and impact, it is important to conduct detailed research of the target audience, including their interests, preferences, consumer behavior and ways of perceiving information; use innovative technologies such as virtual reality, augmented reality and interactive platforms that can help create unique and engaging promotional campaigns that attract the audience's attention and make brands more accessible and interesting.

In today's world, consumers value authenticity and transparency in their interactions with brands. Therefore, it is important that PR campaigns are honest, open and reflect the true values and approaches of a company or individual. Strengthening your social media presence, actively engaging with your audience, publishing interesting and valuable content, and using video and other visuals can significantly increase the effectiveness of PR strategies.

It is important to constantly monitor the effectiveness of PR campaigns, analyze the data obtained and make adjustments to strategies based on this information. Only through continuous improvement can you achieve the greatest success in the show business industry.

4. Conclusions

In today's world, the show business industry has become an important element of cultural and entertainment life, influencing society through various aspects of creativity, communication and art. The study of modern PR strategies in the show business industry reveals important aspects of image, reputation and communication management in this industry. As a result of the study, we can draw the following conclusions:

1. By analyzing effective PR strategies, we can understand that success in this area depends on careful planning, development and implementation of comprehensive communication strategies.

2. The use of social media, organization of press conferences, sponsorship events, online campaigns and other PR tools are becoming key to attracting the attention of viewers, maintaining a positive image and resolving crisis situations.

3. In the show business industry, PR plays a strategic role in supporting and developing artists' careers, successfully promoting creative projects and creating a positive public perception. The starting point for the successful use of PR strategies is an understanding of the audience, market trends, and the ability to interact effectively with various stakeholders.

The scientific novelty. The scientific novelty of the research results is to summarize the theoretical foundations of modern PR strategies in the show business industry and to deepen the understanding of how modern technologies,

social networks, media and other tools affect the ways of communication, support and promotion in the entertainment business. The study of this problem includes the analysis of interaction with the audience, the formation and maintenance of a positive image, the resolution of crisis situations and the use of innovative communication methods. Given the constant changes in consumer behavior and technological capabilities, the study of modern PR strategies in the show business industry allows to develop new approaches to interaction with the audience, increase the effectiveness of communication and achieve the set goals. This research contributes to the development of theoretical foundations and practical aspects of PR in this specific market segment, bringing new insights and recommendations to the show business field.

The significance of the study. The study of modern PR strategies in the show business industry is important in today's media environment. First of all, it contributes to the professional development of communication specialists. The development of the modern show business industry requires constant updating and adaptation of communication strategies for effective interaction with the audience. The findings of the study help to substantiate the most effective approaches and tools for communicating with the public. It allows us to analyze current trends in the field of PR, understand the requirements and expectations of the audience and develop strategies that meet these needs. A deep understanding and use of modern PR strategies allows businesses, artists and other industry players to attract more attention and positively influence the audience's perception. The research contributes to the development of more effective communication strategies aimed at building a positive image, attracting new fans and managing crisis situations. It also opens up new opportunities for the use of innovative technologies and digital platforms in communication strategies.

Prospects for further research. Further research in the field of modern PR strategies in the show business industry opens up great opportunities for a deeper understanding of the interaction between business, artists and the audience. The main areas for future research include analyzing the impact of social media on the reputation and image of show business participants, studying the use of video content and streaming platforms in PR, researching the audience's reaction to crisis situations, and ways to manage reputation. In addition, it is important to analyze the interaction between PR and other aspects of show business, such as marketing and branding. Continuing such research has the potential to reveal new insights and approaches to the effective use of PR strategies, which will benefit both businesses and consumers.

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Information about the Authors:

Anastasia Balan, Bachelor Student, Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts, 36, Ye. Konovaletsia St., Kyiv 01601, Ukraine; e-mail: nastine.balan@gmail.com; orcid id: <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-7948-7811> (corresponding author)

Oksana Krupa, Lecturer, Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts, Kyiv, Ukraine; e-mail: oksanakrupa24@gmail.com; orcid id: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7387-7565>